

Spectrophotometric Studies of Aluminium (III) Quinizarin-2-Sulphonic Acid Chelate

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Aluminium forms in aqueous medium a pink coloured chelate with Quinizarin-2-sulphonic acid. The chelate has the maximum absorbance at 490 nm. The composition and the stability of the chelate has been reported.

Dyes of hydroxyanthraquinone group are well known for their tendency to form coloured chelates with various metal ions. An important member of this group is Quinizarin-2-sulphonic acid.

Quinizarin-2-sulphonic acid forms coloured chelates with many metal ions and has been used as a reagent in analytical chemistry. Aluminium forms coloured chelate with Quinizarin-2-sulphonic acid. No systematic work has been done so far regarding its composition and stability. In the present communication the composition and the stability in the aqueous medium has been reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

BDH A.R. grade ammonium aluminium sulphate and BDH reagent grade Quinizarin-2-sulphonic acid after purification has been used to prepare the solutions.

Absorbance measurements were carried out with the Hitachi Perkin Elmer Uv-Vis spectrophotometer (Model 139). The pH of the solutions was adjusted on a Beckman pH meter. All the measurements were carried out at 25°. Hexamine-perchloric acid buffer was used for pH adjustments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Instantaneous colour change was observed on adding Quinizarin-2-sulphonic solution to the solution containing aluminium metal.

The complex is stable for 3 hrs and after that precipitation starts. The temperature change had a similar effect. The chelate is stable in the pH range 3 to 8. The composition and the stability has been determined at pH 5.0 ± 0.1 .

Nature and stoichiometry of the complex: Vosburgh and Cooper's method indicated that only one complex was formed under the conditions of study having a λ_{max} at 490 nm. Composition of the complex as determined by the three different methods *viz.*, Job's method¹, mole ratio method², and slope ratio method³ at 540 nm and 560 nm and at pH 5.0 ± 0.1 was found to be 1 : 1.

1. P. Job, *Ann. Chimie.*, 1928, (X), 9, 113, 19.
2. J. H. Yoe and A. L. Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.
3. A. F. Harvey and D. L. Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.

Stability of the complex : The stability constant of the complex was calculated by the method of Banerji and Dey⁴, mole ratio method and the method using molecular extinction coefficient data. The value of log K as found by the computation of the values obtained by the above mentioned methods was, 3.10 ± 0.16 . The free energy of the formation was $\Delta F = 4.31 \pm 0.11$ kcal/mole.

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4. S. K. Banerji and A. K. Dey, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1961, **179**, 130.